

Encumbrances of Data Privacy and Ethical Information Use in Nigeria: A Critical Analysis

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19909361>

Abstract

Swift digitalisation has brought unprecedented opportunities and challenges in data privacy and the ethical use of information. In Nigeria, where we are experiencing a burgeoning digital transformation, these issues are compounded by unique socio-economic, technological, and regulatory landscapes. Data privacy in Nigeria is primarily governed by the Nigeria Data Protection Commission (NDPC) and the Data Protection Act of 2023, which mandates explicit consent, purpose limitation, and robust security for personal data. Ethical use of information requires organisations to ensure transparency, accountability, and data subject freedom, especially in light of the growing collection of digital, financial, and biometric data, to avoid misuse and potential regulatory penalties. This paper examines the current state of data privacy and ethical information practices in Nigeria, focusing on the legal framework alongside other relevant legislation, prevalent encumbrances, and their implications. A qualitative research method was employed, utilising document and content analysis, which focuses on understanding the meaning and context of human experiences through observation to produce descriptive, rich data. This paper highlights key ethical dilemmas, including informed consent, data privacy, data monetisation, and government surveillance. Findings reveal that Nigeria ranks 5th globally for the highest number of cybercrime incidents, with an impact rate of 8.25, a professionalism rate of 6.49, and 52.17% of cases involving scams. Findings further reveal a general increase in Nigeria's unemployment rate from the first quarter of 2023 to the second quarter of 2024. Recommendations include strict compliance with data protection laws, reducing the unemployment rate, and increasing cybersecurity manpower, among others.

Keywords: Encumbrances, Data Privacy, Ethical Information Use.

Introduction

Technology has transformed how individuals communicate, how businesses and non-governmental organisations operate, and how governments function. The swift pace of this ongoing transformation is driven by exponential growth in the collection, processing, storage, and use of data. As data-driven innovation delivers significant benefits, it also poses challenges related to personal privacy, autonomy, and the ethical use of information (Floridi, 2018). In Nigeria, navigating this complex landscape is crucial for fostering trust in digital services, protecting citizens' rights, and unlocking the full potential of its digital economy.

Nigeria, with its youthful population, is witnessing a continued expansion of internet coverage and the adoption of digital services across sectors such as finance, telecommunications, e-commerce, agriculture, education, and engineering (Nigerian Communications Commission, 2024). This expansion has outpaced the general public's awareness and the effective implementation of robust data protection mechanisms, leading to high risks of privacy infringement, unauthorised access, data breaches, and unethical exploitation of information.

Research Questions

This article analyses data privacy and ethical use of information in Nigeria. It addresses the following questions:

1. Is there a legal and regulatory framework governing data privacy in Nigeria?
2. Are there ethical implications of data usage for individuals and organisations in Nigeria?
3. Is there a complaint and enforcement agency for data privacy in Nigeria?
4. What are the basic challenges hindering the effective implementation of data privacy and ethical information use in Nigeria?
5. What are the encumbrances and the recommendations that can be put forth to ensure data privacy and ethical use of information in Nigeria?

Addressing the above-mentioned questions, this article seeks to provide an understanding of the encumbrances of data privacy and ethical information use in Nigeria to inform policy-making, industry practices, and public discourse for responsible data governance in Nigeria.

Data privacy concerns the rights and obligations of individuals and organisations regarding the collection, use, and disclosure of personal data (Solove, 2008). It encompasses an individual's ability to control information about themselves. Ethical information use, by contrast, extends beyond legal compliance to consider the moral principles that guide how data is managed, shared, and applied, emphasising fairness, transparency, and accountability (Moor, 1985).

Globally, the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) has set a benchmark for data protection laws, influencing similar legislation worldwide (Voigt & Bussche, 2017). Key principles, including explicit consent, purpose limitation, data minimisation, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity, confidentiality and accountability, form the bedrock of modern data protection.

In the African context, studies have highlighted varying levels of data protection. While some nations have enacted comprehensive laws, others grapple with weak enforcement, limited public awareness, and constrained institutional capacity (Daigle, 2021). Nigeria's journey in data protection is relatively nascent but rapidly evolving. Prior to 2019, data privacy provisions were scattered across sector-specific laws, lacking a consolidated framework. The establishment of the Nigeria Data Protection Commission (NDPC) marked a significant step towards a more unified and comprehensive approach.

Data Privacy in Nigeria

Data privacy is the right of individuals to control how their personal information is collected, processed, stored, retrieved and shared. This right is formally recognised under the Nigeria Data Protection Act (NDPA), which provides the principal legal framework for protecting personal data. The Act established the Nigeria Data Protection Commission (NDPC) as the regulatory authority responsible for enforcement and compliance oversight, as well as for the ethical use of information. While the law establishes rights and obligations, encumbrances arise when practical, structural or systemic factors prevent those rights from being fully realised.

According to the Cambridge Dictionary (2026), an encumbrance is something that makes it difficult for you to do something. Thus, an encumbrance is a restriction that hinders the free exercise of a right or function. In Nigeria, data privacy encumbrances include barriers to the effective enforcement of privacy laws, constraints on individuals' ability to exercise privacy rights, institutional or systemic weaknesses that undermine protection, and technological and socioeconomic conditions that expose personal data to misuse. Thus, encumbrances are not limited to legal shortcomings alone. They include legal and regulatory constraints, institutional limitations, technological vulnerabilities, and socioeconomic realities.

Encumbrances of Data Privacy in Nigeria

As governments, corporations, and individuals generate and process unprecedented volumes of data, safeguarding personal information presents diverse challenges. These challenges can be legal, socioeconomic, technical, or ethical in nature. This classification helps clarify the nature and impact of each constraint. Criteria used for the classification of data privacy constraints include: The Source of the Barrier (whether the challenge originates from laws, social structures, technology, or moral principles); The Primary Domain of Impact (whether the issue affects regulatory systems, economic participation, or human values); The Nature of the Constraint (whether institutional, resource-based, or infrastructural); The Stakeholder Responsibility (whether government, the private sector, or society at large bears primary responsibility).

- 1. Legal Encumber:** Legal encumbrances arise from fragmented regulatory frameworks in data protection across sovereign nations, creating compliance challenges for multinational organisations; jurisdictional conflicts occur when companies operating globally reconcile conflicting national regulations, which can slow innovation and increase compliance costs; weak enforcement mechanisms, including a lack of funding to monitor violations effectively; and rapid technological evolution, such as artificial intelligence and biometric surveillance, which create regulatory gaps. Hence, legal barriers create uncertainty, hinder global data flows, and undermine consistent privacy protection.
- 2. Socioeconomic Encumber:** Socioeconomic constraints stem from disparities in wealth, education, access to basic social amenities, and economic incentives. Power imbalances limit individual users' ability to negotiate privacy terms. Thus, socioeconomic barriers exacerbate privacy inequality, affecting vulnerable populations.
- 3. Technical Encumber:** Cybersecurity manpower shortage is a major technical barrier. Complex Data Ecosystems, such as cloud computing, third-party vendors, and interconnected platforms, increase the risk of data breaches. Cybersecurity threats also expose weaknesses in data storage and transmission systems. Hence, this technical barrier hinders secure data management and increases vulnerability to breaches.
- 4. Ethical Encumber:** Ethical encumbrance involves lengthy, opaque informed consent processes, raising questions about whether consent is genuinely informed. Surveillance and Autonomy erode individual freedom and privacy when used for surveillance purposes. Algorithmic bias may perpetuate discrimination if biased data sets are used, raising concerns about fairness and justice. Balancing Security and Privacy is often justified by governments on national security grounds, creating tension between public safety and individual privacy rights. Thus, the implications of ethical encumbrance challenge the legitimacy and social acceptability of data practices.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this analysis draws on Informational Privacy Theory (Nissenbaum, 2009), which posits that privacy is not merely secrecy but contextual integrity, defined as the appropriate flow of information. It also incorporates elements of Stakeholder Theory (Freeman, 1984), which holds that data practices affect various groups, including data subjects, data controllers, data processors, regulators, and the broader society, each with distinct interests and ethical considerations.

Legal and Regulatory Framework in Nigeria

In 2023, the Nigerian government, headed by His Excellency, President Bola Ahmed Tinubu, GCFR and Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces, established the Nigeria Data Protection Commission (NDPC) as an independent statutory body, replacing the National Information Technology Development Agency's (NITDA) regulatory role in data protection. This move signifies a commitment to strengthening enforcement and regulatory oversight, aligning with global trends towards independent data protection

authorities. Nigeria's drive to ensure data privacy, ethical use, and data processing and storage of information is primarily encapsulated in the following instruments:

The Nigeria Data Protection Act of 2023

The Nigeria Data Protection Act of 2023 is considered the most comprehensive legal instrument guiding the activities of the Nigeria Data Protection Commission (NDPC). It consists of parts that collectively form the basis of data protection governance in the country.

- a) **Rights of Data Subjects:** The Nigeria Data Protection Act of 2023 safeguards the rights of data subjects. The right to be informed ensures individuals are notified about the collection, processing, and purpose. The right to access allows individuals to review data held by organisations, whereas the right to rectify ensures corrections to inaccurate or incomplete data. The right to be forgotten empowers any Nigerian to request the deletion of their data when it is no longer necessary. This also implies that Nigerians have the right to restrict data processing, limiting how their data should be handled in some situations. Furthermore, Nigerians have the right not to be subjected to automated decision-making, ensuring that decisions affecting them are not made solely by automated systems without human intervention. In addition, Nigerians have the right to lodge complaints with the Nigeria Data Protection Commission (NDPC) through its official website to ensure grievances are addressed in accordance with the law. (Nigeria Data Protection Act, 2023)
- b) **Principles of Personal Data Processing:** The Data Protection Act of 2023 establishes key principles to guide the handling of personal data, ensuring fairness, security, transparency and accountability. It also requires that data processing be carried out in accordance with statutory legal procedures. In addition, integrity and confidentiality require the implementation of robust security measures against all forms of data breaches, including loss or destruction (Nigeria Data Protection Act, 2023).
- c) **Lawful Basis of Data Processing:** The Act provides clear legal provisions for processing personal data, ensuring compliance with high ethical standards. Any Nigerian must give consent for the use of their data. Data processing can also be authorised by the data subject to fulfil contractual obligations. In the case of public interest to promote the common good, data processing is permitted. It also permits processing to aid well-established businesses, provided that processing the data of the data subjects does not conflict with the stipulated legal rights of the data subject (Nigeria Data Protection Act, 2023)
- d) **Scope/Application of the Nigeria Data Protection Act:** This Act ensures the comprehensive processing of data relating to data subjects. The Act further governs all data controllers and/or processors operating in Nigeria. Furthermore, the Act also covers data controllers and/or processors not operating from Nigeria but processing the data of Nigerian data subjects. This extraterritorial extension is in line with global data protection procedures, ensuring the protection of all data of Nigerian data subjects is processed, notwithstanding the location of the data processors or controllers (Nigeria Data Protection Commission, 2025).

Cybercrime Act of 2024 (As Amended)

The Cybercrimes Prohibition and Prevention Act of 2015, as amended in 2024, criminalises offences such as hacking, phishing, industrial espionage, plagiarism, ransomware, identity theft, cyberstalking, and online fraud, with penalties ranging from fines to life imprisonment. The Act also contains provisions on unauthorised access, interception, and modification of data, and protects electronic communications. The Act emphasises data protection and cybersecurity, and regulates service providers. The amended Act introduces stricter measures on misinformation and cyberstalking, and mandates that service providers retain traffic data for two years. Thus, offences can lead to fines of up to seven million naira (₦7,000,000) or imprisonment for up to seven (7) years, depending on the severity of the case (Cybercrimes Act, 2024).

National Identity Management Commission (NIMC) Act 2007

The National Identity Management Commission Act repealed the Department of National Civic Registration (DNCR) and established NIMC to create, manage and operate the National Identity Database (NID) in Nigeria. The Act mandates the Commission to register citizens of Nigeria and legal resident migrants, issuing them a unique eleven (11)- digit National Identification Number (NIN) and a General Multi-Purpose Card (GMPC). The Commission is empowered by the Act to ensure the privacy and security of all data subjects' data by securing the National Identity Commission's database. The Act also imposes penalties for illegal registrations, forgery and other offences related to the misuse of the National Identity Document or the GMPC. (National Identity Management Commission Act, 20007)

Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act (FCCPA) of 2018

The Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act of 2018 established the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission to protect consumer interests, prohibit unfair trade practices, and eliminate monopolies. The Act also ensures the right to safe, quality goods, fair contract terms, and redress for substandard services. It further gives consumers the right to clear information on price, quality, ingredients, proper labelling, and protection against unfair commercial practices, including the misuse of data. Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act (2018).

Freedom of Information Act (FOIA) 2011

The FOIA gives Nigerian citizens and organisations the right to access information from public bodies, promoting transparency and accountability. However, the Act provides exemptions for personal information if disclosure might lead to an invasion of privacy. In addition, the Freedom of Information Act also states that information requested by citizens and organisations might be denied if it poses a threat to national security or is protected by other laws (Freedom of Information Act, 2011).

Methods

A qualitative research method was employed, utilising document and content analysis to understand the meaning and context behind human experiences and observations and to produce descriptive, rich data. The criteria considered in selecting the secondary data included the purpose and scope of the paper, the timeliness of the data, its accuracy and reliability, bias and objectivity, and its relevance and applicability. The data used in this study were collated from secondary data sources. The choice of this data source eliminates the need to design, plan, and conduct primary research, saving money and time and providing easy access to quality datasets from online government archives and academic libraries.

Results and Discussions

Table 1: Top 15 countries for cybercrime.

Ran	Country	I	P	TS	WCI	Score (%)	Tech (%)	Attacks(%)	Data (%)	Scams (%)	Cash (%)
1	Russia	8	8.81	8.73	58.39		82.17	81.34	65.18	21.70	41.56
2	Ukraine	8	8.29	8.24	36.44		52.97	50.76	36.01	11.20	31.27
3	China	8	7.70	7.81	27.86		40.22	24.24	34.89	15.83	24.13

4	USA	7	7.21	7.21	25.01	27.64	17.68	30.36	22.72	26.63
5	Nigeria	8	6.49	5.80	21.28	7.93	8.41	23.04	52.17	14.86
6	Romania	7	7.04	7.15	14.83	17.89	9.17	22.50	13.15	11.49
7	N. Korea	7	7.23	7.83	10.61	8.66	25.33	13.01	2.17	3.88
8	UK	7	7.21	6.75	9.01	5.04	4.75	5.80	7.86	21.63
9	Brazil	6	6.35	6.32	8.93	13.70	8.77	10.29	7.28	4.64
10	India	7	6.60	6.65	6.13	4.46	3.62	6.81	12.75	3.01
11	Iran	6	6.45	6.64	4.78	8.62	10.00	3.59	0.94	0.72
12	Belarus	6	7.20	7.32	3.87	11.92	5.58	1.85	--	--
13	Ghana	8	6.83	6.09	3.58	1.23	0.76	2.97	10.36	2.57
14	S. Africa	6	5.35	5.50	2.58	1.20	0.65	0.58	7.17	3.30
15	Moldova	7	7.19	7.56	2.57	6.70	0.98	2.43	0.83	1.88

Source: World Cybercrime Index (2024).

I = Impact; P = Professionalism; TS = Technical skill; Tech = Technical products/services; Attacks = Attacks and extortion; Data = Data/identity theft; Cash = Cashing out and money laundering. I, P, and TS are scored out of 10.

Table 1 above ranks Nigeria 5th globally for the highest number of cybercrime incidents, with an impact rate of 8.25.

Professionalism: Table 1 shows that Nigeria ranks 13th with a professionalism score of 6.49. Professionalism, which refers to the ethical status, methods, character, or standards expected of a professional or its organisation(s) (Nigeria Data Protection Commission), encompasses reliability, discretion, even-handedness, and fair play. These qualities can be discouraged by socioeconomic barriers, such as underpaid enumerators and unhealthy working conditions. These conditions give rise to unethical conduct. Such conduct creates vulnerability in data privacy and the ethical use of information.

Technical Skills: The NDPC, though newly established, requires significant skilled personnel to effectively monitor compliance, investigate breaches, and prosecute offenders in accordance with the Nigeria Data Protection Act of 2023 and other related Acts. However, Nigeria, with 5.80 in the TS column of Table 1, ranks 14th among countries with cybersecurity skills. This is a clear indication of a significant shortage of manpower in the country's cybersecurity sector. This, in turn, leads to the NDPC's inability to maintain data privacy and ethical use of information, as fatigue and human error arise from increased workloads and pressure.

Data/Identity Theft: With 23.04% in Table 1, Nigeria ranks 5th globally and 1st in Africa for data/identity theft. Most Small and Medium-scale Enterprises (SMEs) lack the financial capacity and professional acumen to implement adequate data security measures. This leaves them vulnerable to cyber attacks, leading to an increase in data breaches.

Technical products/services: Nigeria's vibrant acceptance of technological advancement is characterised by rapid innovation in Artificial Intelligence (AI), Data Science, online banking systems and e-commerce. As such, start-ups often prioritise speed to market and user acquisition over robust privacy-by-design principles. Nigeria, with 7.93%, ranks 10th in the world for technical products/services. Thus, striking a balance between fostering innovation and ensuring strict data protection becomes an encumbrance for the Nigerian Data Protection Commission.

Scams: Nigeria, with 52.17% in the scam column, automatically ranks as the country with the highest scam rate in the world. However, Nigeria's status as the country with the highest scam rate in the world can be attributed to poverty, driven by a high unemployment rate. Thus, scams become the fastest means to an end, as cybercriminals employ dumpster diving, social engineering and phishing techniques to exploit their victims. Hence, this encumbers data privacy and ethical use of information.

Table 2: Key Labour Market Indicators

Key Labour Market Indicator	Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023
Unemployment Rate	4.1	4.2	5.0
Youth Unemployment Rate	6.9	7.2	8.6
Urban Unemployment Rate	5.4	5.9	6.0
Rural Unemployment Rate	2.9	2.5	4.0

Source: Nigeria Labour Force Statistics Report (2024)

Labour market indicators show the general unemployment rate increasing from 0.1% in Q1 to 0.8% in Q2 and 0.9% in Q3 of 2023. The youth employment rate shows a progressive increase from 0.3% in Q1 to 1.4% in Q2 and 1.7% in Q3 of the same year. The urban unemployment rate increases by 0.5% from Q1 to Q2 and by 0.1% from Q2 to Q3, with a net increase of 0.6% between Q1 and Q3 of the same year. The rural unemployment rate decreased by 0.4% between Q1 and Q2, but increased by 1.5% between Q2 and

Q3 in the same year. The Nigeria Labour Force Survey of Q1 2024 further indicates an unemployment rate of 5.31%, and 4.26% in Q2 of 2024.

Impact: The rapid pace of technological advancement and acceptance in Nigeria poses a significant challenge to data protection regulation. Emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence, big data analytics, and the Internet of Things (IoT), create new loopholes in personal data gathering and processing procedures, requiring the continuous adaptation of regulatory policies, legal oversight and enforcement mechanisms. This technological evolution makes it difficult for the Nigerian Data Protection Commission to keep up with the trend. However, Table 1 indicates an impact rate of 8.25, placing Nigeria in 4th position in the world cybercrime index's impact column.

Conclusion

Nigeria is at a crucial stage in its digital transformation. While the NDPC makes a significant step by establishing a legal framework for data privacy, implementing and ethically applying these principles remains challenging. Encumbrances to data privacy go beyond legal rules; they include practical, institutional, technological, socioeconomic, and ethical barriers that hinder the realisation of data protection rights under the Nigeria Data Protection Act. Essentially, these constraints prevent data privacy from becoming a fully protected and enforceable right in Nigeria's growing digital society. Overcoming these obstacles requires not only robust laws but also institutional capacity, technological safeguards, and ongoing policy efforts. Priorities such as increasing public awareness, strengthening regulatory enforcement, promoting privacy-by-design, cultivating an ethical data culture, and engaging in international cooperation will support ethical data privacy and responsible information use. This approach will protect citizens' fundamental rights, build trust, encourage innovation, and unlock the potential of Nigeria's expanding digital economy, ensuring data is a means for progress rather than exploitation.

Recommendations

The following were recommended

1. Strengthen Regulatory Enforcement and Independence

The establishment of the NDPC is a positive step. However, it must be adequately funded, staffed with skilled professionals, and granted genuine operational independence to enforce the NDPA effectively. This includes proactive monitoring, timely investigations, and consistent application of penalties to deter non-compliance by organisations. Collaboration with other regulatory bodies (e.g., NCC, CBN, EFCC, NIMC) is crucial.

2. Enhance Public Awareness and Digital Literacy

Massive public awareness campaigns, utilising local languages and diverse media channels, are needed to educate Nigerians about their data privacy rights, the NDPA, and safe online practices. Digital literacy programmes should be integrated into the Nigerian educational system and community initiatives to empower citizens to make informed decisions about their personal data. Copyright law and information ethics should be integrated into the Nigerian university curriculum as a course.

3. Foster a Culture of Ethical Data Governance

Businesses and government agencies need to cultivate an internal culture that prioritises ethical data handling, going beyond mere legal compliance. This requires strong leadership commitment, regular employee training in data ethics, clear internal policies, and mechanisms for the ethical review of data-intensive projects.

4. Judicial Clarity and Oversight

Clearer legal interpretations and robust judicial oversight mechanisms are required, particularly regarding government access to personal data, to balance national security needs with fundamental data subject privacy rights.

5. International Cooperation and Harmonisation

Engaging in international dialogues and aligning with global best practices (e.g., the African Union Convention on Cybersecurity and Personal Data Protection, amongst others) can strengthen Nigeria's data protection framework and facilitate cross-border data flows, which are essential to the digital economy.

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